

Deep water and lowland rice germplasm collection and evaluation in North Bihar

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North Bihar has more than 2 million ha of rice, 80% of which is grown in poorly drained and deep water areas. We began collecting germplasm from those areas in 1978 and have identified 350 varieties: 90 deep water rices and 260 lowland rices. All varieties identified, except intermediate TCA20-1, 20-2, 212, and 217, were tall. Some were evaluated for yield, yield characters, and drought tolerance.

Three deep water environments were identified, based on water depth: medium deep water (about 1 m); deep water (up to 2 m); and very deep water (4-5 m). Twenty very deep water varieties were identified.

Deep water rices had longer panicles with more grains per panicle than lowland varieties. Very deep water rices had the most grains per panicle (140-324). Lowland rices had 72-164 grains per panicle.

Drought can be a problem in these areas. In Mar 1979, 65 varieties were direct-seeded in deep water tanks. There was a severe drought in May-Jun and many entries died. TCA2, 4, 7, 8 (deep water varieties), and TCA9, 13, 14, 16, 20, 21, 26, 30, 35, and 38 had drought resistance.

Promising deep water and lowland cultures, North Bihar, India.

Collection no.	Grain color	Kernel color	Elongation	Suitability	Additional information
TCA4	Straw	Red	Better	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA11	Straw	Red	Better	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA176	Black	Red	Better	D. W.	
TCA177	Black	Red	Best	D. W.	BB resistant
TCA191-1	Black	Red	Best	D. W.	
TCA20-1	Straw	White	Better	D. W.	
TCA55	Straw	White		M. D.	Wider adaptability
TCA78	Black	Red	Good	M. D.	
TCA162	Gold	White	Better	M. D.	Long glume
TCA179-3	Black	Red	Better	M. D.	
TCA21/TCA22	Straw	Red	Good	S. D.	Sturdy stem
TCA43	Straw	White		S. D.	
TCA47	Gold	White		S. D.	
TCA148-3	White	White		S. D.	
TCA127	Gold	Red	Good	S. D.	
TCA48	Gold	White		S. D.	
TCA49	Black	Red		S. D.	
TCA72	Straw	Red		S. D.	
TCA83	Straw	Red		S. D.	Wider adaptability
TCA20-2	Straw	White	Poor	S. D. & L. L.	Sturdy stem
TCA20-3	Straw	White	Poor	S. D. & L. L.	Sturdy stem
TCA190-1	Black	White	Poor	L. L. & S. D.	RTV resistant scented
TCA58	Straw	Red		L. L.	Wider adaptability
TCA108/TCA149	Straw	Red/White	Poor	L. L.	Wider adaptability
TCA212	Straw	White	Poor	L. L.	
TCA227	Brown	White	Poor	L. L.	

^a D. W. = deep water, M. D. = medium deep, S. D. = shallow deep, and L. L. = lowland. BB = bacterial blight, RTV = tungro.

In 1979 and 1980, the varieties were entered in yield nurseries. Twenty-six cultures were identified as promising and entered in multilocation tests (see table). TCA47 and TCA148-3 yielded 3.1 t/ha in shallow or medium deep water.

TCA177 yielded best in deep water and Barogar 5 and Barogar 6 yielded best in medium deep water — about 2.7 t/ha. Varieties tended to yield best under the water regimes from which they were collected. □

NC492, a promising rice for waterlogged fields in West Bengal

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We evaluated 18 elite rice cultures for growth and yield attributes in waterlogged fields (see figure) in the Gangetic Plains of West Bengal in kharif. Eight varieties had better than 70% survival (see table). Days to 50% flowering ranged from 118 to 150. OR330-40-3 flowered earliest and CR292-5258 and CR292-7050 flowered last.

Total dry matter production varied widely. BIET807 accumulated 1,308 g

Changes in rainfall and water depth in the experimental field in 1983 kharif, Calcutta, India.

dry weight/m² and PLA1100, 242 g. Survival percentage appeared to substantially influence dry matter production,

irrespective of days to flowering or maturity. Tilakkachari produced 255 panicles/m², followed by NC492 with